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IMPROVING CHILDREN'S SENSORY INTEGRATION CAPABILITIES WITH RICH INTERACTION DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, more and more children are found to have learning or behavior problems when they enter school. Some of them are diagnosed as having insufficient sensory experience in their childhood. To prevent this kind of problem, it is important to provide proper sensation stimulations during a child's development. In this paper, the development of an interactive device for one-year-old infants will be demonstrated. The design integrates visual and auditory sensations to motivate young children's body motion. It also provides various tactile sensations to enrich their sensitivities to touch. Based on the result of user evaluation with the prototype, the design concept proves useful in improving young children's sensory capabilities.

Keywords: Sensory Integration, Design for Children, Toy, Infancy.

INTRODUCTION

Having new born babies is the happiest time for families. However, due to the crowded living environments, busy parents, and even grandparenting, some infants were forced to grow up in limited spaces with inadequate activities (Gao, 1994). They were not able to obtain sufficient sensory experience in their optimal learning periods. As a result, those children are very likely to have learning problems later in their lives (Burton, 1980). As an example, take the case of Tom who was raised by his grandparents in the countryside, while his parents were both working in the city. Because Tom's grandparents were not very healthy and didn't like to clean up the toys or storybooks disturbed by Tom, his childhood was quite limited in obtaining visual or

audio sensory experience. When he entered elementary school, he was found to have difficulties in recognizing Chinese characters, pronouncing words, and even speaking simple sentences (Gao, 1994, p. 115). To prevent such kind of problems, A. Jean Ayres (2005), the founder of the Sensory Integration Theory, pointed out that if the adults could provide the children proper sensory stimulations to learn how to organize their sensations in the first seven years of life, they will have an easier time learning mental and social skills later on.

In general, sensory integration is a person's ability to organize sensations around him/her for use. For normal adults, the successful sensory integration involves the following processes (Mauro, 2006, p. 3):

1. Receiving the sensory information successfully.
2. Interpreting the sensory information correctly.
3. Combining information from different senses to create a complete picture.
4. Deciding on a response based on information from all sources.
5. Executing that response by sending electrical impulses back out to the muscles and limbs.

Among these processes, the neurons in a human brain are the most important elements in completing tasks. In an average person, there are about twelve billion neurons in the brain. Each neuron consists of a cell body and a fiber that connects to thousands of other neurons. The flow of signals through the complicated network produces our learning and behavior. According to recent research (Ayres, 2005), it was found that most newborn infants have the same number of neurons an average adult has. However, infants have very few interconnections between their neurons. To develop their interconnections, it is necessary to stimulate the

neurons. The growth of new interconnections produces new possibilities for neural communication. Each new interconnection adds new elements to the child's sensory perceptions and motor abilities. The more neural interconnections a person has, the more capable he is of learning. This means that the parents or the care teachers need to provide infants the necessary "food" of sensations to form sensory and motor processes that will remain relatively stable for the rest of his/her life. In recent years, many scientists have found the importance of the children's development in the first 3 years (Zero To Three, 2008). In this period, the growth process could be divided into the following three stages:

1. **Young infants** (Birth to 9 months) seek *security*.
2. **Mobile infants** (8 to 18 months) eagerly engage in *exploration*.
3. **Toddlers** (16 to 36 months) continue to form their *identity*.

Recently, there has been much research focusing on the interaction designs for children (Hourcade, 2008). One of the trends is tangible computing (e.g. Fishkin, 2004; Hornecker, 2009) which facilitates the flexibility of computing to provide rich experience and learning opportunities. In this research, we focused on the study of mobile infants and developed a tangible device which is aimed to provide rich sensations to improve young children's capacities in sensory integration.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Although the diagnosis of sensory integration disorder might be new to many people, the disorder isn't a new concept in children's health (Mauro, 2006). There are several different terms used to describe related problems, such as *Sensory Integration Dysfunction*, *Sensory Processing Disorder* (SPD) etc. Recently, more and more researchers are devoted to investigating related studies. For example, Ahn, Miller, Milberger, and McIntosh (2004) found that 5.3% of kindergarten children's daily lives is affected by SPD. In another study with elementary school-aged children, it was suggested that 16% of children experience sensory challenges sufficient enough to disrupt their academic, social, and/or emotional development (Ben-Sasson, Carter, & Briggs-Gowen, 2009). In the United States of America, 5% to 15% of children, without other disabilities,

have sensory processing problems (Mauro, 2006). Most of those problems are due to the incomplete development of their sensory systems during their early childhood (Ayes, 2005).

Based on the process of successful sensory integration mentioned previously, the first important step is to receive sensory information correctly. A normal human have eight senses to obtain the information of oneself and the environment. Those sensations can be categorized in three levels (Ayes, 2005). The first level is the traditional five senses (sight, sound, taste, smell, and touch) that tell us what is coming from outside the body. The second level includes the proprioceptive and vestibular senses which respond to movement, gravity, and body position. They tells us how and where the body is moving. The third level relates to the senses within our internal organs that tell us about the inside of the body.

<p>Level 1: Sensations that tell us what is coming from outside the body (Exteroceptors)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sight (or Visual Sense) • Sound (or Auditory Sense) • Taste (or Gustatory Sense) • Smell (or Olfactory Sense) • Touch (or Tactile Sense)
<p>Level 2: Sensations that tell us where the body is in space and how it is moving (Proprioceptor)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Position and Movement (Proprioceptive Sense) • Gravity, Head Movement, and Balance (Vestibular Sense)
<p>Level 3: Sensations that tell us about the inside of the body (Interoceptors)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visceral Sense

Figure 1. The three levels of sensations (Ayes, 2005, p. 38).

It takes a long time for an infant learn to integrate this sensory information and to make proper actions. The process can be visualized as the four levels shown in Figure 2 (Ayes, 2005). Some of the sensory inputs are integrated with the others first, while others are integrated later. To be clear, everything develops together, but some functions lead up to others.

1. In first level (around 2 months), an infant's nervous system is working a great deal at the primary level of integration. The vestibular and proprioceptive senses are integrated and lead to well-organized eye movements, physical balance, and gravitational security. In addition, the touch sensations from every bit of skin come together for several types of use.

Figure 2. The process of sensory integration (Ayres, 2005, p. 55)

- In 2nd level, an infant will learn to integrate the three basic senses—tactile, vestibular, and proprioceptive—to form a body percept, to improve coordination of the two sides of the body, to undertake motor planning, and to have emotional stability.
- Around 1 years of age, the 3rd level is becoming more important as auditory and visual sensations enter the process. First, the auditory and more vestibular sensations come together with the body percept and related functions to enable the child to speak and understand language. Visual sensations are integrated with the three basic senses to give the child detailed visual perception and eye-hand coordination.
- At age 3, when an infant is working on the above three levels, he or she has also begun the 4th level which involves all sensory inputs to form

multiple capacities. It is around age 6 that the first two levels are mostly complete, while the 3rd and 4th levels have become active and important.

METHODS

USER STUDIES

Before starting to develop the design concepts, we observed the daily activities of two infants at their homes. The time of each visit was about two hours, and the duration of the observation was five days. The ages of the two participants were 14 months and 12 months. At the time of the study, they had been starting to learn to walk for more than 1 month. They were both very good at crawling. Based on our observations, we found the following three interesting points for creating the design ideas:

1. Mobile infants are very likely attracted by bright objects, such as spot lights. One day we tried using a laser flashlight to play with a participant. She was attracted to the bright spot on the floor and tried to crawl continuously to catch it. This game could last about five minutes. A photo of the trial is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. A field study with the 1-year-old participant.

2. The second thing we found from the field study is the natural vitality and sensitivity regarding the rhythm of songs. The participants were very likely to twist their bodies along with the music. This kind of tendency is also found in some other outdoor or indoor activities we undertook. We suggest that music material could be effectively used to trigger young children's body movement in the interaction design.
3. Finally, in these two participants' houses, there were various kinds of toys the parents offered to their babies. Most of the toys embedded different stimuli of sensations, such as auditory, visual, or tactile. However, there are very few products aimed at encouraging infants' body movements. This is also found in several toy stores we visited and surveyed. On this point, Benzwie (1987) found that body movement is central to learning for young children. Based on the rich experience in teaching young children dance for more than 50 years, Barlin and Kalev (1989) suggested that superior intelligence could be developed simultaneously with superior body skills. The movement exercises could help establish children's self-esteem and confidence

along with the brain and body development. Moreover, these activities could catapult the child high above the average. Chi and Liu (2006) also found that dance and body movement can strengthen a person's sensation capabilities, stimulate multiple parts of the brain, and help to develop the entire brain.

CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT

For sensory integration problems, Mauro (2006) found that the tactile, proprioceptive, and vestibular senses are the "big three" sensations. If they couldn't operate well, the other senses will not work properly. In addition, because moving our bodies involves multiple sensations (sight, touch, proprioceptive and vestibular senses), a design aimed at encouraging an infant's body movement might be helpful in increasing children's capabilities in sensory integration. Based on this assumption, a tangible interactive device was developed in this study.

In the beginning, the category classification approach of the Kansei Engineering method (Nagamarchi, 2002) was used to develop our design ideas. The aim of encouraging body movement was set as the zero-level concept and then broken down to subconcepts. The classification process was repeated several times until we reached the appropriate features which could be mapped to the sensations. The result of the diagram is shown in Figure 4.

Several design concepts were then developed based on the classifications. After evaluating the ideas with some other interaction designers, the "Shinning stage" concept was selected for implementation. The sketch of this concept is shown in Figure 5. It provides multiple sensation experience (visual, auditory, touch, proprioceptive and vestibular senses) and the lighting effect is used to encourage infants' movement and exploration. There are two major components in this concept.

Figure 4. The expanded structure of the main design concept.

Figure 5. The design sketch of the "Shinning Stage for Mobile Infants" concept

sensations for the infants. Under some pieces of the floor boards, the touch sensors will be embedded as triggers for the device.

When a child steps on the sensitive boards, the system will play a specific piece of song (about 25 seconds) with a lighting effect. One of the effects is that the 50 LED bulbs will be turned on/off in sequence to form moving lights that could trigger the infant to move to catch them.

Using the metaphor of theater stage, the device is intended to motivate the mobile infant's body movement like a dancer dancing on the stage. Through this kind of stimulation, it will be able to help young children improve their capabilities to integrate multiple sensation information, understand the different directions and movements, and be able to control his or her body and have sensitive balance.

PROTOTYPING

The prototype was implemented with the Arduino Mega 2560 platform. First, 50 LED bulbs in five different colors were installed on the top frame.

1. On the top frame, there are 50 LED bulbs with different colors installed around the border. Among the bulbs, there also are two kinds of illumination (bright [30mA] and normal [10mA]) which can provide different stimulations to the young children.
2. On the ground, there is a stage full of multiple materials that will provide rich tactile

Figure 6. The prototype of the “Shining Stage for Mobile Infants” developed in this research.

Each one is controlled independently. Through programming the lighting sequence, six different effects were created. Second, multiple touch sensors were installed under 6 wooden boards on the ground. After conducting several trials with one participant, the song “Ob-la-di, Ob-la-da” (from the “All You Need is Love: Beatles Songs for Kids” album) was selected as the song for making the prototype. The edition we chose is performed by children and is slightly reworked in kid-friendly keys. The rhythm is also very clear and lively. Most of the time when the participants listened to this song, they began to swing along with the rhythm. Therefore, this song might be helpful in encouraging a young baby’s movement on the “Shinning Stage”.

The “Ob-la-di, Ob-la-da” song was cut into six different pieces. The length of each clip is about 20 seconds. When a baby steps on the specific wooden board, it will trigger the specific lighting mode with a piece of sound. The interaction mechanism is developed and run with the Adobe

Director 11. A photo of the prototype is shown in Figure 6.

INITIAL USER EVALUATION RESULTS

In order to understand the effect of the design concept, seven families with young children were invited to evaluate the prototype. The ages of the infants were between seven to 18 months. Two of the six infants could not stand alone and walk. In general, it took about five minutes for the infants to feel comfortable in the strange environment and the device. Also, five of the participants began to swing their arms on the stage. The main findings are summarized as follows:

1. Two participants (aged around 1.3 years old) moved to catch the moving lights more than three times. This suggests that the flowing design could help mobile infants practice and improve their motor planning skills.
2. The moving lights also led the infants to explore the richness of the materials used in the floor boards. However, one of the participants cried

after touching the soft and fluffy pad (the two black pads shown on the far right side of Figure 6). The parents told us that he feared to touch unfamiliar things. For example, when they went to parks, he was afraid at touching anything, even a leaf.

3. In this concept, we tried to build up the floor boards with normal materials which could be found in common families' homes. The parents can even replace the boards with any boards of the same demension, which means they can add some materials their babies are familiar or unfamiliar with. This will help to provide rich tactile "food" to improve their sensitivity to touch.
4. Four of the participants noticed and focused on the lights; some of the parents even used it to communicate with their babies. They pointed to the LED bulb and told the baby the name of the color. One participant even raised his hands up and tried to touch the lights.
5. Most of the participants tended to swing their arms along with the music. Surprisingly, their body movements were in sync with the rhythm of the song. This suggests that the design also helps trigger the integration of auditory and vestibular sensations.
6. During the experiment, we found that one of the parents liked to sing songs to their baby. The prototype was designed so that the infants will trigger a specific sound by tapping on specific floor boards. To involve the parents, it would be a good and useful idea if the auditory material could be easily replaced with the children's songs that parents sing with their children in daily life. In the future, we will try to include this customization function in the next version.

CONCLUSIONS

Most children are born with natural aptitude in music and dance (Chang, 2004; Lee, 2002). In this research, a design concept of "Shinning Stage for Mobile Infants" was developed and implemented for improving young children's capability in sensory integration. Based on the user evaluations with the prototype, it was found that auditory sensation plays an important role in motivating babies' body movement. The various tactile sensations on the

floor boards also encourage some participants to move around and explore the differences in touch sensations. Together with the harmonious lighting effects, it makes the space a special stage for the young children to express their creativity.

From the evaluation, another interesting point was found. The design concept described in this manuscript was set to be used by a single infant. However, during the user evaluation, it was also found that this device could be utilized by multiple infants, as well. Some participants liked to interact with others while playing. In the future, we will study this social interaction issue and extend the richness of the device.

REFERENCES

- Ahn, R. R., Miller, L. J., Milberger, S., & McIntosh, D. N. (2004). Prevalence of parents' perceptions of sensory processing disorders among kindergarten children. *American Journal of Occupational Therapy, 58*(3), 287-293.
- Ayres, A. J. (2005). *Sensory integration and the child* (25 ed.). Los Angeles: WPS.
- Barlin, A. L., & Kalev, N. (1989). *Hello toes! : Movement games for children*. Pennington, NJ: Princeton.
- Ben-Sasson A., Carter A. S., & Briggs-Gowan M. J. (2009). Sensory over-responsivity in elementary school: Prevalence and social-emotional correlates. *Journal of Abnorm Child Psychol, 37*(5), 705-716.
- Benzwie, T. (1987). *A moving experience :Dance for lovers of children and the child within*. Tucson, AZ: Zephyr Press.
- Burton, E. C. (1980). *Physical activities for the developing child*. Springfield, Ill: Thomas.
- Chang, N. W. (2004). 兒童音樂治療 [Music therapy for children]. Taipei: Psycho.
- Chi, H. V., & Lui, C. G. (2006). 舞蹈美育原理與教程 [The beauty of dance: Theory and teaching method]. Shanghai: Smph.
- Dissanayake, E. (2008). If music is the food of love, what about survival and reproductive success? *Musicae Scientiae, 12*(Spec. Iss.), 169-195. Retrieved March 20, 2011, from http://www.ellendissanayake.com/publications/pdf/MS-SpecialIssue_2008-Dissanayake.pdf
- Fishkin, K. P. (2004). A taxonomy for and analysis of tangible interfaces. *Personal and ubiquitous computing, 8*(5), 347-358.
- Gao, L-G. (1994). 感覺統合：上篇 [Sensory integration: Part 1]. Taipei: Hsin-Yi Publishing.
- Hornecker, Eva (2009). *Tangible interaction*. Retrieved 15 June, 2011, from http://www.interaction-design.org/encyclopedia/tangible_interaction.html
- Lee, C. T. (2002). 非常愛跳舞—創造性舞蹈的心體驗 [Experiencing creative dance]. Taipei: Psygarden Publishing.
- Mauro, T. (2006). *The everything parent's guide to sensory integration disorder: Get the right diagnosis, understand treatments, and advocate for your child*. Avon, MA: Adams Media.
- Nagamachi, M. (2002). Kansei engineering as a powerful consumer-oriented technology for product development. *Applied Ergonomics, 33*(3), 289-294.

Rock, A. M., Trainor, L. J., & Addison, T. L. (1999). Distinctive messages in infant-directed lullabies and play songs. *Developmental psychology, 35*(2), 527-534.

Schellenberg, E. G., Nakata, T., Hunter, P. G., Tamoto, S. (2007). Exposure to music and cognitive performance: Tests of children and adults. *Psychology of Music, 35*(1), 5-19.

Valentin, S. R. (2005). Commentary: Sleep in German infants-the "cult" of independence. *Pediatrics, 115*(1), 269-271.

Zero to Three. (2008). Caring for infants & toddlers in groups. Washington, DC: Zero to Three